

TALKING ABOUT AGE IN ENGLISH

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When talking about their age, people usually give an exact number, for example: I'm twenty nine (I'm twenty-nine). When talking about a third person whose age is not known accurately (or would not like to disclose), the expression in his\her teens\twenties\thirties\forties and so on is often used. Let's look at the expression **she is in her forties** as an example ; it's difficult to find an exact Russian analogue; literally the expression means that she is over forty and under fifty, from 40 to 50 years old. Ten years is a pretty big difference, isn't it? For clarification, words are often added:

- early - the first of ten years;
- middle — the middle of the ten-year range;
- late - closer to the next ten.

For example: *She is in her early forties - She is just over forty (somewhere 41-44).*

Here are more examples:

- The guy is in his early teens - The guy is a little over ten.
- His sister is her middle twenties - His sister is about twenty-five (about 24-26).
- Our CEO is young, he is in his late thirties - Our CEO is young, he is somewhere around forty (about 36-39)

Let's also take a closer look at the words denoting age groups. When talking about children, the words baby, toddler and child are usually used. There is no strict framework that baby is from so many to so many years, but most often by baby we mean babies, starting from infancy, by toddler children of approximately kindergarten (in our understanding) age, and child - from about 4 years old -6 and up to adolescence. This division is quite arbitrary; you can call a baby a child.

At the age of 12-13, a child enters a stormy adolescence and now he is no longer a child, but a teenager, or teen for short. Every teenager dreams of finishing school as quickly as possible, moving away from their parents and becoming an adult. Please note that the word adult is not used to indicate age. Adult is an adult as opposed to a child or teenager. The age after 60 (somewhere earlier, somewhere later) is usually called advanced, respectable, and in English senior. The expression old man\woman sounds disrespectful (especially old

woman), much like our “old man\old woman” or “grandfather\grandmother.” Senior or elderly is a more polite option.

We talk about body shape without hurting anyone's feelings.

If a man suddenly talks to a woman about her age, it will seem rude and impolite to her, but if he is so reckless that he dares to discuss her figure, a slap in the face cannot be avoided. Speaking about figure, build, appearance, you need to remember that there are characteristics only for women (for example, fine - miniature), only for men (handsome - handsome), there are stylistically neutral characteristics (overweight - obese), and there are sharp, rough ones (fat - thick, greasy).

Female characteristics: slim (slender), neat (graceful), petite (miniature), pretty (beautiful).

Male characteristics: slender (slender), lean (slender, thin), well-built (well-built), handsome (handsome).

As for rough and non-rough characteristics, they relate to the most delicate issue of excess weight. The simplest, most obvious, but rude way to say that a person is fat is to call him or her (the latter is dangerous) fat, that is, fat, fat. A plump man can quite easily be called a plump man (full) or simply a big guy (big). With women it is much more difficult. When talking about a lady in the third person, you can use the following expressions:

- pleasantly plump lady - an old-fashioned, but quite polite expression, in Russian there is an exact equivalent “lady of pleasant plumpness”;
- full-figured - “full”, also a rather polite expression used in relation to women;
- curvy lady is a hard-to-translate expression, something like “a lady with curves.”

In general, it's better not to talk about your figure again.

The sensitive issue of ethnicity in the US

It is better not to raise the issue of ethnicity, especially if you are in a foreign country and do not know its cultural characteristics well. However, when describing appearance, the issue of nationality is difficult to avoid. I'll tell you how they usually speak in the USA, a country in which the issue of friendship between peoples has been very painful throughout history. The main ethnic groups in the United States are:

- White Americans (or simply white) - white Americans.
- African Americans (or afroamerican) - African Americans.
- Asian Americans - Americans of Asian descent.

- Latin Americans - Latin Americans.
- Native Americans - Native Americans, that is, Indians.

In general, these expressions are the most neutral. Speaking about the third person, you can calmly say: He is white\Afroamerican\Asian\latin American.

Note: There is a difference between the words nationality and race. Nationality usually means citizenship, and the above words white, Asian, etc. are race, that is, race or ethnicity.

The most long-suffering term on this list that has undergone a long evolution is African Americans. It is not surprising, given the difficult path this part of the population has gone through in the United States. Until relatively recently, it was considered normal to say negro (Negro), now this word is considered rude, later Americans began to say colored or black Americans (colored or black Americans), but now African Americans are considered the norm. The word "black" is most often not considered offensive, but depends greatly on the context. This is a very terrible insult. The only thing worse than calling a woman fat.

List Of References:

1. Zokirova, S. (2023). From the History of the Formation of Neurolinguistics. American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education (2993-2769), 1(6), 74–79.
2. Zokirova, S. M., & Nuriddinova, M. S. (2023). The First Step in the Development of the New Textbook Education System. Web of Synergy: International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, 2(5), 98-104.
3. Абдупаттоев, М., & Зокирова, С. (2019). КОНГРУЭНТЛИК ҲОДИСАСИ ВА УНИНГ КОНТРАСТИВ ЛИНГВИСТИКАДАГИ ЎРНИ. Farg ‘ona davlat universiteti ilmiy jurnali, (2), 22-22.
4. Zokirova, S. (2023). From the History of the Formation of Neurolinguistics. American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education (2993-2769), 1(6), 74–79.

